

EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS.

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Bacterial vaginosis (BV) is a very common disease of the vaginal ecosystem that requires timely diagnosis, comprehensive and adequate treatment. The use of intravaginal forms of ascorbic acid affects the main mechanisms of BV pathogenesis and increases the effectiveness of treatment.

Keywords: bacterial vaginosis, ascorbic acid, treatment.

Despite significant advances in modern technologies in clinical microbiology and pharmacology of modern antibacterial drugs, bacterial vaginitis and vaginosis continue to occupy a leading place in the structure of obstetric and gynecological diseases [1].

Bacterial vaginosis develops due to an imbalance of the vaginal microflora when *Lactobacillus* spp. they are replaced by conditionally pathogenic microorganisms (for example, *Gardnerella* spp., *Prevotella* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp.). Bacterial vaginosis increases the risk of developing genital infections in women and pregnancy complications. Bacterial vaginosis has been proven to be a cofactor of the development of papillomavirus infection.

In modern conditions, inflammatory diseases of the genital organs are characterized by a number of features: an increase in the importance of conditionally pathogenic flora, an increase in antibiotic resistance of microorganisms, a change in the clinical picture – asymptomatic, erased forms, atypical course. All this creates certain difficulties in the diagnosis of diseases. According to a number of researchers, these features are based on disorders in the immune system.

The concept of microbial biofilms, which are associated with the majority of human bacterial infections, including BV, has been developed and scientifically justified [9]. *G. vaginalis* has a unique ability to form a so-called biofilm on the surface of the urogenital mucosa. Biofilm is a conglomerate of microorganisms located on a surface whose cells are attached to each other. Usually the cells are immersed in the extracellular polymer substance (extracellular matrix) secreted by them - mucus. It is believed that 95-99% of all microorganisms in the natural environment exist in the form of biofilm. Microorganisms form a biofilm under the influence of a number of factors, including cellular recognition of attachment sites to the surface and the presence of nutrients or aggressive substances,

oxygen, etc. In the biofilm formation mode, the cell changes its behavior, which is caused by the regulation of gene expression.

It is this biofilm, like cement or glue, that attracts other microorganisms to itself, forming a conglomerate of bacteria, most of which have a pathogenic or, at least, a dangerous effect for humans. Biofilms were found to consist mainly of *Gardnerellavaginalis*, while *Atopobiumvaginae* was present in 80% of cases and accounted for 40% of the biofilm mass. Other bacteria are much rarer, including bacteria belonging to the genera *Bacteroides*, *Corynebacterium*, *Lactobacillus*, *Veillonella*, *Ruminococcus* and *Streptococcus* [10]. Currently, it has been established that the vaginal biotope is a balanced system in which the acidic environment of the vaginal contents controls the presence of microbial strains, and the microflora, in turn, provides or does not provide the acidity of vaginal secretions. The key elements of this ecosystem are the vaginal epithelium and vaginal flora [5]. To date, there are many ways to normalize the disturbed vaginal flora. As a rule, antibiotics and disinfectants are most often used, followed by lactobacilli in terms of frequency of use. However, it is often not taken into account that the state of the bacterial background is determined by many factors, one of which is the acidity of the medium [7]. You can inject lactoflora into the vagina as much as you like against a background of high pH – it will be ineffective. Acidity (pH) determines the survival of both lactoflora and pathogenic bacteria, the physiological medium acidic environment (pH <4.5) does not allow pathogenic microorganisms to multiply.

The issues concerning the effective therapy of infections caused by microorganisms forming microbial biofilms remain unresolved [2,6]. In this regard, the use of medications that reduce the pH of the vaginal discharge is promising for the treatment of BV. An example of such a therapeutic agent is the intravaginal drug Motheris ("World Medicine Ilach San. Vetij.A.Sh.", Turkey), the active substance of which is ascorbic acid (AK). In the light of modern knowledge about the role of cohesive *G. vaginalis*, which forms microbial biofilms, it may be justified to use topical (intravaginal) forms of AK. By lowering the pH of the vaginal environment, it is able to indirectly influence the elimination of factors for the realization of pathogenic potencies of conditionally pathogenic microorganisms and to a certain extent prevent the formation of biofilm [2]

Local application of ascorbic acid helps to restore physiological acidity by lowering the pH when dissolving ascorbic acid in the vaginal discharge. Against this background, the barrier function of MPE improves, colonization by

lactobacilli occurs [3], and activation of local immunity due to ascorbic acid, which stimulates the formation of antibodies and improves the phagocytic function of leukocytes [4]. In addition, it participates in the exchange processes of connective tissue. Altered collagen metabolism and deterioration of its quality at the same time contribute to clinical manifestations of connective tissue dysplasia at the pelvic floor level – lowering of the vaginal walls, urinary incontinence. The alkaline environment of the vagina with hypoestrogenism accelerates the progression of these processes. Ascorbic acid, stimulating the fibroblast system and contributing to the formation of collagen [4], contributes to the maintenance of the connective tissue structure. The restoration of the normal pH level of the vagina begins after 2 hours after the BB.

Motheris is a natural remedy created on the basis of an innovative approach to the restoration and maintenance of physiological levels in the vagina. From the standpoint of evidence-based medicine, it is an effective alternative to hormone therapy in patients who do not accept it or have contraindications to its use, for example, during breastfeeding, after chemotherapy. The appearance of itching and burning when using Motheris may be caused by a candidiasis infection, which requires laboratory analysis to diagnose candidiasis vaginitis and prescribe appropriate treatment. We examined 60 non-pregnant women aged 18 to 45 years, the average age was 28.3 years with a diagnosis of bacterial vaginosis. Women who took antibiotics in the last two weeks preceding the examination or used douches and topical medications (ovules, suppositories, vaginal pills, tampons, and others) were excluded from the study. The patients were divided into 2 groups of 30 people: patients were included in the 1st group, as therapy, who were offered a scheme that included 1 tablet of Motheris intravaginally 250 mg / day per night for 6 days (for acidification of the medium and destruction of bacterial films), then Metronidazole vaginal suppositories of 500 mg twice a day for 7 days. Group 2 patients received traditional metronidazole intravaginal therapy 500 mg 2 times a day for 7 days. The composition of the examined women by age, general and obstetric-gynecological anamnesis did not significantly differ.

The patients had the most frequent complaints of discomfort in the genital area (a collective concept combining the subjective phenomena of vaginal syndrome - pathological discharge from the genital tract, itching and/or burning). Among all, the recurrent course of the disease prevailed, the frequency of which reached 3-4 times a year. Screening diagnostic tests were used to diagnose bacterial vaginosis: 1) the pathological nature of vaginal discharge was assessed; 2) the

pH of the vaginal discharge; 3) identification of key cells by microscopic examination of wet unpainted preparations of the vaginal discharge, where mature epithelial cells with microorganisms adhered to them (gardnerella, mobiluncus, gram-positive cocci) were determined. With the cultural method of examination, all patients had a marked decrease in the number of lactobacilli and an increase in the content of opportunistic flora. Results of the study: After treatment of BV, the following parameters were evaluated:

- Subjective complaints of the patient (presence/absence of general discomfort, itching, pain, burning, presence/absence of characteristic secretions)
- Objective clinical symptoms (during examination and palpation – hyperemia, swelling, soreness, presence/absence of characteristic secretions)
- Laboratory parameters (number of leukocytes, presence of key cells, qualitative and quantitative composition of vaginal microflora in microscopic and bacteriological studies)
- Presence of lactobacilli in microscopic examination of vaginal discharge at the end of therapy

In the future, clinical and laboratory monitoring was carried out 2 weeks after the end of treatment and 3 months later in order to establish the absence of a relapse of the disease. According to the results of the examination conducted 14-16 days after the end of therapy, it was revealed that in the treatment of BV by the complex method with the inclusion of Motheris in the first clinical group of patients, the presence of abundant vaginal discharge was observed in 10% (3), a specific odor – 0.0%, the pH of the contents of the vagina more than 4.5 – 3.3% (1), key cells -0.0%. In 95% (29) of cases, complete normalization of the vaginal microflora was noted, while in the treatment of BV Metronidazole in patients of the second group, the presence of abundant vaginal discharge was observed in 6.7% (2), a specific odor of 9.7% (3), the pH of the contents of the vagina was more than 4.5 – 6.7% (2), key cells - 3% (1). Metronidazole therapy was ineffective in 10% (3) of cases. After 3 months after the end of treatment, BV relapsed in 6.7% (2) women of the first clinical group and, with accordingly, in 16.6% (5) of the second clinical group. According to the results of the examination conducted 3 months after treatment, it was revealed that in 1 group of patients, the presence of abundant vaginal discharge was observed in 10% (3), a specific odor – 3.3% (1), the pH of the contents of the vagina more than 4.5 – in 3.3% (1), key cells -6.7% (2). In patients of the second group, the presence of abundant vaginal discharge was observed in 16.6% (5), a specific odor of 13.3% (4), the pH of the contents of the vagina was more than 4.5 – 13.3% (4),

key cells -16.6% (5). Thus, the pathogenetic therapeutic strategy in BV, based on a decrease in the pH of the vaginal environment, provided a more persistent and long-lasting therapeutic effect of antibacterial drugs, which prevented the occurrence of relapses of BV for 3 months in the vast majority of the examined patients. The inclusion of ascorbic acid (Motheris) in the therapeutic scheme of BV contributes to the stable restoration of the vaginal microbiota for a long time period compared with monotherapy with antibacterial drugs.

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